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A SMALL VILLAGE IN THE TOWN:
AN *EUCERA* NESTING SITE IN PISA

Un piccolo villaggio nella città: un sito di nidificazione di Eucera a Pisa

Ecological research on animal diversity in urban ecosystems is rapidly growing. Urban environments are suitable to provide habitats for a variety of animals, including insects, birds, reptiles and amphibians, small mammals, such as bats, rodents, moles, hedgehogs, small carnivores and ungulates, wild boars, and more recently also wolves (REYNOLDS *et al.*, 2021). Recently, the idea that urban areas can provide an important source of habitats and resources also for pollinator populations, is emerged (VILLALTA *et al.*, 2021). While urbanisation contributes to the biodiversity loss, cities themselves can also be part of the solution to the problem by harbouring declining populations of pollinators threatened by intensively managed rural areas (HALL *et al.*, 2017). There is increasing evidence of the role of cities as a refuge for pollinators, especially wild bees (HERNANDEZ *et al.*, 2009; CARIVEAU & WINFREE, 2015; SIROHI *et al.*, 2015). Urban ecosystems have been shown to often maintain a higher degree of pollinator diversity than many rural landscapes. Neighbouring agricultural areas can even profit from a rich urban pollinator community (LANGELLOTTO *et al.*, 2018; WENZEL *et al.*, 2020). Many researchers are thus calling for conservation programs for urban pollinators.

In this framework, “bee-hotels” consisting of trap-nests, are increasingly set up in urban green area. However, the usefulness of these trap-nests to promote native wild bee populations is under debate, as there is evidence of greater use of the nests by exotic species. This can pose a

threat when exotic bees show aggressive and competitive behaviour towards native wild bees (QUARANTA *et al.*, 2014; GESLIN *et al.*, 2020). In this scenario, the study and monitoring of populations of ground nesting bees, which represent the majority of bees generally nesting in cities (PRENDERGAST *et al.*, 2022), becomes important.

A little observation study of an aggregation of nests of *Eucera nigrescens* (Pérez, 1879) in an urban environment was carried out in Pisa (Tuscany, Italy). *E. nigrescens* is a monovoltine, ground nesting solitary bee species, belonging to the longhorn bee tribe Eucerini, in the Apidae family (MICHENER, 2007). Eucerini bees are an important and common guild of long-tongued pollinators in the Mediterranean regions whose biology is still poorly studied and not fully clarified (SHEBL *et al.*, 2016). They are known to dig tunnel-like nests in the ground with vertical, elongate brood cells lined with a waxlike secretion. Nesting activity of *Eucera* bees usually begins in early spring and lasts until May. Females emerge around one week after males and start the mating season, lasting 3-4 weeks, after which females engage in nest building and provisioning (MICHENER, 2007).

An aggregation of 59 nests of *E. nigrescens* was found in the city centre of Pisa (43°40'51.45"N 10°20'50.96"E), covering an area of approximately 15 m² of a road verge (Figs. 1a, b). The nests were marked with numbered sticks and the area was checked daily for the presence of bees during the last two weeks of April. The presence of a few males (2-3 individuals) patrolling the nest area was observed. One specimen was collected for taxonomic identification. At the end of April, it can be assumed that the mating period is at an end, which explains the scarcity of males.

During the observation period, nesting females were captured, marked with a coloured entomological sticker on the thorax and released. Five females were found. It can be assumed that the nesting females were more, but that their nest-building and egg-laying activity had already finished at the time of observation. It was also possible that a number of nests had been abandoned or remained empty from the previous year. Nesting females were observed arriving at the nest with loads of pollen on their corbicules, entering the tunnels and leaving after a few minutes, after depositing the pollen in the brood cells. The flowering observed in the area near the nests, available for foraging, were dandelion (*Taraxacum spp.*), daisy (*Bellis perennis*), buttercup (*Ranunculus spp.*), gypsyweed (*Veronica spp.*) and other flora present in the gardens of neighbouring houses.

In addition, a *Nomada* bee was observed inspecting nests. *Nomada*

(Scopoli, 1770) is a genus of cleptoparasitic bees in which females lay eggs into host brood cells, already provisioned with pollen. Host eggs or larvae are then killed by the emerging *Nomada* larva. *Nomada* bees mainly parasitized the bee genus *Andrena*, but some species are known to be parasites of bees belonging to Melittidae and Halictidae families (MICHENER, 2007). Parasitisation of the families Colletidae and Apidae by *Nomada* has only been hypothesised (ALEXANDER, 1994).

This small report aimed to highlight how an urban city centre environment can be a source of bee biodiversity to be protected. Even small interventions, such as requesting the urban green management authorities not to mow the nest area, can be important for the conservation of pollinator populations in cities. Urban areas should not be overlooked in wild bee monitoring plans. Intensifying the efforts for improving the urban wild pollinator communities, exploiting the potential of cities as refuge for bees and other insect pollinators, can open new areas of research.

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Fig. 1 — Road verge where the nests aggregation of *E. nigrescens* was found (a) and detail of two nests entrance (b). Some of the nests marked with sticks are indicated by the white frames (a).

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